

CONSIDERATION OF ELASTOPLASTICITY AND VISCOPLASTICITY DURING THERMOMECHANICAL FATIGUE SIMULATIONS OF A PIPE BEND USING THE FEM-IMPLEMENTED PRANDTL OPERATOR APPROACH

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In this paper, the results of a metallic pipe bend are presented which is subjected to a variable thermomechanical load history and then its stress-strain response is simulated using the FEM-implemented Prandtl operator approach. This method has recently been extended to consider the division of the total strain into elastoplastic and viscoplastic parts using the non-unified theory. This consideration is especially important at higher temperatures where viscoplastic properties of the material become more significant. A critical location on the pipe bend was chosen and examined from the simulated stress-strain point of view. Six different operating conditions were simulated. It has been shown that a far more critical stress-strain response can be expected if the temperature-dependent viscoplastic material properties are considered during the exposure to variable thermomechanical loads. Moreover, the complexity of the stress-strain response considerably increased with increased load temperatures.

Keywords: Prandtl operator, Finite element method, Thermomechanical loading, Plasticity, Pipe bend, Fatigue

INTRODUCTION

Products are subjected to variable operational loads during use. These loads can originate either from the environment, from their use and even as a consequence of their material properties, size and form. Power-plants, exhaust systems of road vehicles or propulsion systems of air-crafts are typical examples (Avila Molina et al. [1], Bartošák et al. [2], Dondapati et al. [3], Li et al. [4]). The purpose of early-stage development evaluations is thus on one hand to estimate the typical operational loads. On the other hand, the response of the product to these loads is to be assessed. Several evaluations are typically performed to achieve this goal (Avila Molina et al. [1], Beltrán and Pino [5], Bartošák et al. [6], Zhang et al. [7]). After the evaluation of functionality and suitability for manufacturing with available technologies, a structural analysis is usually carried out which provides the basic insight into the behaviour of the product during the operation. However, as the products are expected to endure a prescribed number of operating hours, a durability evaluation followed by a reliability analysis is a common next developmental step (Klemenc and Nagode [8], Gu et al. [9]). If the product fulfils the project requirements it is then handed over to the prototype production and the beginning

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of testing. Otherwise, another design iteration is carried out to change the material properties, shape or size of the product.

Modern R & D evaluations markedly depend on the quality of the stress-strain simulations in the product as a response to external loading (Avila Molina et al. [1], Bartošák et al. [2], Dondapati et al. [3], Li et al. [4]). While there are various techniques available for analysing the performance of products during their operation, the finite element (FE) method, which has been extensively researched for decades, stands out as one of the most commonly employed approaches in modern computer-aided engineering (Kumar et al. [11]). It is now effortlessly possible to retrieve the information on the displacement, stress or strain fields in every part of the product at any instant during operation. This then allows for a comprehensive examination of critical points, but also for exploration of redesign possibilities by altering the geometry, dimensions or material characteristics of the products under investigation. Moreover, a diverse range of material models is available within both open-source and commercial FE environments. These models enable consideration of both typical and unique material properties, including elastoplasticity, viscoplasticity, kinematic or isotropic hardening and cyclic softening. Nevertheless, new or specialised material models can be included in FE environments via user-defined material models (Bartošák et al. [2], Šeruga and Nagode [12], Nagode et al. [13]). These custom models must be implemented at the integration point level of a finite element. They generally take the estimated strain tensor and temperature increments as input and provide the resulting stress tensor increment as output.

The Prandtl operator approach has initially been designed to simulate uniaxial temperature-dependent stress-strain response and predict both high-cycle and low-cycle fatigue damage of structural components under variable thermomechanical loads (Nagode and Fajdiga [14], Nagode et al. [15], Nagode and Šeruga [16]). It has since been implemented into the FE environment to consider cyclic elastoplastic material behaviour (Šeruga and Nagode [12], Nagode et al. [13]) and recently, consideration of viscoplastic material properties has been added (Nagode et al. [17]). Although the original uniaxial version of the Prandtl operator approach already considers both modelling of elastoplastic and viscoplastic (creep) behaviour and separate prediction of fatigue/creep damage (Nagode et al. [18], Šeruga et al. [19]), the current FE-implemented version (Nagode et al. [17]) considers the material-modelling part of the approach. The implementation of the fatigue/creep damage prediction is planned for future work. A calculation of a pipe bend subjected to thermomechanical loads has already been analysed by Šeruga et al. [20], but elastoplastic properties only of a ferritic stainless steel EN 1.4512 have been considered there. Here, the consideration of elastoplastic and viscoplastic behaviour is studied for 10 CrMo 9 10 steel. A brief description of the stress-strain simulation algorithm is given first, summing up how the non-unified theory of elastoplastic and viscoplastic strains using the Prandtl operator approach has been suggested. The boundary conditions and the loading histories of the pipe bend are given next. Finally, the results are discussed in terms of the observed behaviour under various operating conditions.

METHOD

The closed-form solution of the FE-implemented elasto-viscoplastic Prandtl operator approach is used to seek for the determination of the stress tensor increment as

$$\Delta\sigma_{ij} - 2\mu^*(T)\Delta\varepsilon_{ep,ij} + \lambda^*(T)\Delta\varepsilon_{ep,kk}\delta_{ij}. \quad (1)$$

Here, $\Delta\varepsilon_{ep,ij}$ is the calculated elastoplastic strain tensor increment and $\mu^*(T)$ and $\lambda^*(T)$ are elastoplastic Lamé constants (Nagode et al. [17]). The latter depend on elastoplastic material properties, given by the temperature-dependent Prandtl densities $\alpha_l(T)$, and radial backstrains E_{pl} ; $l=1, \dots, n_q$ in the Prandtl model which enable the consideration of multilinear kinematic hardening. The elastoplastic strain tensor increment $\Delta\varepsilon_{ep,ij}$ is calculated from

$$\Delta\varepsilon_{ep,ij} = \Delta\varepsilon_{ij} - \Delta\varepsilon_{vp,ij} \quad (2)$$

where $\Delta\varepsilon_{ij}$ is the given strain tensor increment and $\Delta\varepsilon_{vp,ij}$ is the calculated viscoplastic strain tensor increment, gained from the relation

$$\Delta\varepsilon_{vp,ij} = \frac{3}{2} \frac{s_{ij}}{|\sigma_{eff}|} \dot{p} \Delta t. \quad (3)$$

The time increment and stress deviator tensor are denoted by Δt and s_{ij} , respectively, and the effective viscoplastic strain rate $\dot{p}$ follows the law of perfect viscoplasticity with elastic domain as

$$\dot{p} = \text{sign}(\sigma_{eff}) \left\langle \frac{\sigma_{eff} - k(T)}{K(T)} \right\rangle^{N(T)} \quad (4)$$

where $k(T)$, $K(T)$ and $N(T)$ stand for the temperature-dependent viscoplastic material parameters. Effective stress σ_{eff} follows from the radial stress in deviatoric plane s_p as

$$\sigma_{eff} = \sqrt{\frac{3}{2}} s_p \quad (5)$$

and s_p is modelled in terms of a Prandtl operator as

$$s_p = \sum_{l=1}^{n_q} \alpha_l(T) E_{pl}, \quad (6)$$

where radial back-strains E_{pl} depend on the elastoplastic strain tensor $\Delta\varepsilon_{ep,ij}$ from Eq. 2. Importantly, the stress deviator tensor s_{ij} and the effective stress σ_{eff} in Eqs. 3 and 4 refer to the values at the beginning of the time increment Δt which enables the calculation loop by use of the forward integration scheme (Nagode et al. [17]).

The stabilised cyclic stress-strain conditions and viscoplastic behaviour for 10 CrMo 9 10 steel in this study have been described by the Ramberg-Osgood relationship and Norton law, respectively, for four temperatures between 23 °C and 500 °C. The resulting cyclic curves are given in Fig. 1 and the resulting material parameters are provided in Table 1. The Prandtl densities α_l ; $l=1, \dots, n_q$ for the test temperatures have been calculated from the curves as described in Nagode et al. [17] whilst interpolation has been used for other temperatures. The Prandtl densities and Norton material

parameters are calculated and stored prior to the simulation which ensures a high computational power of the approach (Nagode et al. [17]).

FIGURE 1 a) FE mesh of the pipe bend with boundary conditions, b) temperature-dependent elastoplastic material properties of 10 CrMo 9 10 steel and c) applied load histories consisting of internal pressure, mechanical load and temperature.

TABLE 1 Material properties for 10 CrMo 9 10 steel at test temperatures of 23 °C, 300 °C, 400 °C and 500 °C (Boller and Seeger [10])

T [°C]	R_m [MPa]	E [MPa]	K' [MPa]	n' [-]	k [MPa]	$N \ln K$ [MPa]	N [-]
23	627	210000	842	0.118	862.8	40.08	4.838
300	553	204100	773	0.119	374.2	17.56	1.3324
400	530	187800	688	0.1029	296.6	14.13	0.8018
500	466	184800	500.3	0.0773	238.9	11.03	0.3034

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A pipe bend with the outer diameter of 100 mm and the wall thickness of 5 mm has been subjected to three different variable load histories as depicted in Fig. 1 and defined in Table 2. 68000 nodes and 48000 solid finite elements of type C3D8 (8-node linear bricks) have been used to create the structural mesh of the pipe bend. One end of the pipe bend has then been fixed whilst the other end

has been loaded with a prescribed displacement as shown in Fig. 1. Every step lasted 1000 s. Additionally, internal pressure of 10 bar has been applied to the internal side of the wall initially and then kept until the end of each loading (Fig. 1). The temperature load has followed three paths (Fig. 1). In the first step (between 0 and 1000 s), the temperature has risen from 23 °C to 300 °C. Then in the fourth step (between 3000 s and 4000 s), the temperature has changed to either 400 °C (Temperature 1), 450 °C (Temperature 2) or 500 °C (Temperature 3). Combined by consideration of either elastoplastic only or elasto-viscoplastic material properties, six operating conditions have thus been designed as given in Table 2. The results of the simulations are presented in Figs. 2-7.

TABLE 2 Evaluated operating conditions for the pipe bend in this study

Designation	Considered conditions
Operating condition 1	Temperature 1 & elastoplasticity
Operating condition 2	Temperature 2 & elastoplasticity
Operating condition 3	Temperature 3 & elastoplasticity
Operating condition 4	Temperature 1 & elasto-viscoplasticity
Operating condition 5	Temperature 2 & elasto-viscoplasticity
Operating condition 6	Temperature 3 & elasto-viscoplasticity

FIGURE 2 Equivalent stress distribution in the pipe bend after step 3 considering a) operating conditions 1, b) operating conditions 2, c) operating conditions 3, d) operating conditions 4, e) operating conditions 5 and f) operating conditions 6. Magnification factor equals 25.

Specifically, Figs. 2-3 present the equivalent von Mises stress field on the pipe bend for the pipe bend at steps 3 and 7, respectively, and Figs. 4-7 present the simulated strain and stress tensor results at the observed location on the pipe bend (Fig. 1).

FIGURE 3 Equivalent stress distribution in the pipe bend after step 7 considering a) operating conditions 1, b) operating conditions 2, c) operating conditions 3, d) operating conditions 4, e) operating conditions 5 and f) operating conditions 6. Magnification factor equals 25.

As the temperature is equal for the six simulated operating conditions after 3000 s, negligible differences in the results are obtained comparing either considered elastoplastic or elasto-viscoplastic material properties (Fig. 2a vs. 2d or Fig. 2b vs. 2e or Fig. 2c vs. 2f). Moreover, the results between operating conditions 1-3 and 4-6, respectively, do not differ either as the same temperature is applied in this instant regardless of the operating condition. On the contrary, after 7000 s (Fig. 3), the discrepancies between the results increase with increasing temperature if viscoplasticity is considered. Fig. 3a vs. 3d, Fig. 3b vs. 3e and Fig. 3c vs. 3f show the differences for the temperatures 400 °C, 450 °C and 500 °C, respectively. Furthermore, the change in the stress response can be noticed comparing Figs. 3a, 3b and 3c if elastoplastic response only is considered.

Furthermore, Fig. 4 clearly shows a variable multiaxial response at the observed location on the pipe bend for operating conditions 1-3. The highest strain-tensor components appear in directions 33 and 13 with an amplitude reaching 0.15 % of strain. The values of strain are substantial also in the other directions, too. However, the temperature change after 3000 s slightly changes the course of the strain signal due to the temperature-dependent elastoplastic properties. As the material resistance decreases with increasing temperature, discrepancies are observed for operating condition 1, 2 and 3. Considering viscoplastic material properties in operating conditions 4-6, a more expressed variable multiaxial strain response is gained after 3000 s at the observed location on the pipe bend (Fig. 5). Until 3000 s, a similar behaviour is observed as in Fig. 4. After 3000 s however, strain levels

exceeding 0.7 % are observed with the highest values for the highest temperature (operating condition 6) for all the strain-tensor components.

FIGURE 4 Strain tensor response at the observed location with considering elastoplastic material properties only. Orange colour represents mechanical loading with internal pressure, magenta stands for the first load cycle at 300 °C. Blue, green and red colour represent the second load cycle at raised temperature.

FIGURE 5 Strain tensor response at the observed location with considering both elastoplastic and viscoplastic material properties. Orange colour represents mechanical loading with internal

pressure, magenta stands for the first load cycle at 300 °C. Blue, green and red colour represent the second load cycle at raised temperature.

Examining the stress tensor response at the observed location on the pipe bend for operating conditions 1-3 (Fig. 6) and 4-6 (Fig. 7), similar assessments can be drawn. Operating conditions 1-3 yield the same stress response until 3000 s and produce discrepancies after that time due to the temperature-dependent elastoplastic material properties (Fig. 6). The stress-tensor components for operating condition 3 are thus always below those for operating condition 1 due to the reduced material resistance at increased temperatures. A more complex behaviour is observed when temperature-dependent viscoplastic material properties are considered, too (Fig. 7). The stress signal can show a more intricate course especially for operating condition 6 due to a significantly reduced load-bearing capability of the whole pipe bend. This can also be seen in the shape of the pipe bend in Fig. 3.

FIGURE 6 Stress tensor response at the observed location with considering elastoplastic material properties only. Orange colour represents mechanical loading with internal pressure, magenta stands for the first load cycle at 300 °C. Blue, green and red colour represent the second load cycle at raised temperature.

FIGURE 7 Stress tensor response at the observed location with considering both elastoplastic and viscoplastic material properties. Orange colour represents mechanical loading with internal pressure, magenta stands for the first load cycle at 300 °C. Blue, green and red colour represent the second load cycle at raised temperature.

CONCLUSIONS

Thermomechanical fatigue is very often the decisive mechanism which determines whether the structural component will perform the intended function throughout the design lifetime or not. Finite element method (FEM) has been most commonly used R&D evaluation tool for the determination of the stress-strain response during the simulations of the operational load on the structural component. Fatigue damage predictions, which are based on the results of the finite element analyses (FEA), are thus directly influenced on the considerations of material phenomena in FEA. The extended FEM-implemented Prandtl operator approach can hence provide an insight into the contributions of both elastoplastic and viscoplastic material properties to fatigue damage predictions. The analysed pipe bend, subjected to variable thermomechanical loads, showed that with consideration of temperature-dependent elasto-viscoplasticity a far more critical stress-strain response can be expected than if only elastoplastic material properties were considered.

LIST OF SYMBOLS

- $\alpha_i(T)$ temperature-dependent Prandtl densities
- δ_{ij} Kronecker delta tensor
- $\Delta\varepsilon_{ij}$ given strain tensor increment
- $\Delta\varepsilon_{ep,ij}$ elastoplastic strain tensor increment

$\Delta \varepsilon_{vp,ij}$	viscoplastic strain tensor increment
E_{pl}	radial backstrains
$k(T)$	first temperature-dependent viscoplastic material parameter
$K(T)$	second temperature-dependent viscoplastic material parameter
$\lambda^*(T)$	first elastoplastic Lamé constant
$\mu^*(T)$	second elastoplastic Lamé constant
$N(T)$	third temperature-dependent viscoplastic material parameter
σ_{eff}	effective stress
s_p	radial stress in deviatoric plane
$\Delta \sigma_{ij}$	stress tensor increment
s_{ij}	stress deviator tensor
Δt	time increment

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